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**ENRICHING THE LEXICON OF THE GLOBAL LANGUAGE:
A CONSTRAINT-BASED STUDY OF YORÙBÁ BORROWINGS IN BRITISH
ENGLISH**

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Abstract¹

Studies in contact linguistics on Yoruba and English have often suggested that the English language has always loaned to the Yoruba language, with the latter not reciprocating in any significant way. It has often been assumed that Yoruba can never enrich the lexicon of a ‘superstrate’ language like English, or so the thinking goes. Such a narrow thinking precludes the need for any research in the opposite direction. This study argues that borrowings between Yoruba and English are bimodal –from top to bottom, and from bottom up. The latter is the focus of this study. The study argues that English borrowings from the Yoruba language are necessitated by linguistic needs rather than stylistic passion. Contrary to what obtains in literature, this study claims that such other-language-lone items are better described as non-established borrowing or borrowing for short, rather than nonce borrowing or codeswitching which may require a certain level of competence in both languages. Using 10 lexical items from three dictionaries, the study found that Yoruba borrowings in English enrich rather than weaken the grammatical potency of Standard English. In addition, the borrowed forms cannot yet be described as established loans. The findings further revealed that while the markedness constraint **AGREEPLACE (nasal)** requiring adaptation that favours RL morphophonological inventory is active in all cases

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considered; there is no such thing as tone-stress mapping in Yoruba borrowings in English. The study concludes that Yoruba borrowings in English have come of age; more studies will need to be conducted in order to discover their contributions to contact linguistics. The study recommends more research to be carried out in African contact linguistics.

Keywords: Borrowings, borrowing, Yoruba, British English, Optimality Theory

Introduction

The contact between Yorùbá language, a Defoid, Benue-Congo or Yoruboid language subgroup of the West Benue-Congo phylum, with English, a language belonging to the Germanic family group of languages (Good, 2017; Horobin, 2018; Kessler, William and Leben, 2017) has been both ways – while the former has borrowed from the latter; the latter has also borrowed from the former. However, since the morphophonologies of English and Yorùbá are not co-terminus, the researcher wonders how a number of issues, especially in Yorùbá borrowings to English would be resolved at borrowing stage. This curiosity, among other things necessitated the present study.

Two reasons necessitated this study. First in the year (2020), a number of new words were added to the *Oxford English Dictionary* (OED) as loanwords. Some of these loaned words were from Yoruba, a Benue-Congo language spoken largely in Nigeria, West Africa. The acceptance of these words into the OED was an indication that the Yoruba language has not stopped enriching the lexicon of the English language. Although to many, that seemed to be the first time the Yoruba language would be supplying lexical items to enrich the lexicon of the English language, such a view cannot be correct. Available records show that Yoruba words have always been used in Standard British English as evidenced in the number of such words found in the *Daniel Jones English Pronouncing Dictionary*, and the *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary* (OALD).

Second, Britain, the ancestral home of the English language is fast becoming more multilingual than ever. Botticello (2015) reports that there is Lagos in London. By the phrase 'Lagos in London', Botticello is referring to the multilingual community in London, where the Yorùbá

language is spoken alongside British English and other non-indigenous languages. That community is characterized by Yoruba cuisines, drinks and fashion. This then mean that apart from purely linguistic reasons, sociolinguistic and sociocultural forces have also made it necessary to investigate Yoruba loanwords in English. The present study however, focuses on the linguistic aspect, with special reference to lexical borrowing from Yoruba into English.

Therefore, it must be stated at this stage that this study is not an addition to the growth of Nigerian English. That area of study has a huge research resources available for any interested researcher. This is a study in British English linguistic borrowing.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the adaptation strategies characteristic of Yoruba lexical borrowing in the lexicon of the English language, with Yoruba as the source language (SL), and English as the recipient language (RL).

Research questions

The following two research questions are answered in this study:

- i. What are the adaptation strategies characteristic of Yoruba borrowings in the lexicon of the English language?
- ii. How can the findings of the study be formalized within Optimality Theory (OT)?

Language contact and contact linguistics

The field of linguistics which studies what bilinguals do with language, and the various manifestations of languages in contact such as codeswitching, codemixing, borrowing and other contact-induced changes is called contact linguistics. Language contact occurs when speakers of, often, mutually unintelligible languages interact in a linguistic context through their languages. Among the manifestations of such interactions are *language convergence*, *relexification* and *borrowing*. Language convergence is a linguistic situation in which two languages become *structurally* similar as a result of long mutual co-existence, irrespective of the language family

they belong to. Language convergence can be at any level of linguistics, including phonetics and phonology.

Relexification refers to the linguistic situation, in which all or much of the lexicon or vocabulary of a language is changed due to contact without any commensurate change in the grammar of the relexified language as it is usually the case with pidgins and creoles. Shodipe (2015) argues that relexification is an in-group language use which is an evidence of linguistic deviance and a move towards linguistic autonomy. It is characterised by language innovation, coinage and devernacularization. Muysken (2000) classifies relexification and calquing as forms of insertional aspects of lexical semantic interference. Relexification then is an important aspect of bilingual practice. It is a process of linguistic lexical borrowing which is characterised by much lexicon and native item replacements.

Linguistic borrowing

Language change is inevitable because bilingualism and multilingualism are everywhere (Lightfoot, 2011). Wardaugh and Fuller (2015, p. 131) explain that “no language is completely isolated and it is possible to argue that most languages develop in contexts in which there is some multilingualism”. Significantly, Trudell (2009, P.1) observes that “Multilingualism is a gift, a resource. No one knows this better than Africans do”. This, therefore, means that nowhere else have there been studies on bilingualism and language contact than Africa. An important manifestation of language contact is borrowing

Borrowing is a linguistic metaphor for lexical and post lexical appropriation and adaptation of linguistic elements of one language by another language at contact point (Aalberse & Muysken, 2019). Although Weinreich, (1953, p. 112), mentions Troubetzkoy (1928) as being among the earliest linguists to refer to “union of languages” or “linguistic area”, a field that has grown in recent times to become contact linguistics, the field of language contact really dates back to Whitney (1881) who discovered that borrowing is a linguistic reality because no language is self-sufficient. According to him, as long as humans come in contact, one language speaker is liable to borrow linguistic item from another language user.

A key aspect of lexical borrowing is loanword, morphemic importation of lexical constituents without substitution. Loanwords can either be assimilated or unassimilated into the RL. At times, both the integrated loanwords and its un-integrated counterparts are used. The choice of any type or form of loanwords often depends on the frequency of use, and preference of speakers of the RL (Gardani, Arkadiev & Amiridze, 2015).

2.1.2. Previous studies on English-Yoruba contact

The study of the contact between Yoruba and English can be categorised into two. The first category comprises lexical borrowing with investigation on, and analysis of loanwords. Such studies include, among others, Salami (1982), Ajolore (1982), Ufomata (1991), Kenstowicz (2006), Taiwo and Adeniyi (2011), Orié (2018), and Oyinloye (2020) The works of Salami (1982) and Ajolore (1982) are related. Both Salami (1982) and Ajolore (1982) investigate how lexical items from English are adapted into Yoruba. Like others before them, they also focus mainly on Yoruba-English borrowing. Adegbija's (2004) study focuses on the plight of Nigerian indigenous languages under the domineering arm of European languages, such as French and Portugues, but most especially, the English language.

Bamiro' (1994) and Adegbija's (1989) studies are devoted to the investigation of the lexico-semantic variation in Nigerian English. Their studies investigate not only the lexico semantic changes that have taken place in Nigerian English. They also mention some of the lexico-semantic contributions of the Yoruba language to the vocabulary of Nigerian English. The works of Ufomata (1991) and Kenstowicz (2006) are related. Both of them discuss how tone and stress relate in lexical loans. Kenstowicz' paper finds that English primary and secondary stress patterns are adapted as Yoruba high tone and low tone respectively. He feels that Nigerian English may be the proximate source of loan or borrowing by the Yoruba speakers of English in Nigeria. Taiwo and Adeniyi (2011) invstigate the emergence of consonant clusters in Yoruba English loans. Oyinloye (2020) is among the first work to examine the adaptation of complex vowels in English.

His findings show that English diphthongs and triphthongs are adapted into Yoruba through the processes of deletion and lengthening. He and Kenstowicz formalize their studies within the Optimality Theory.

The second category is the study of structural borrowing manifested in codeswitching and codemixing. The codeswitching and codemixing scholars (Amuda, 1994; Bamiro, 2006; Lamidi, 2009; an Akande, 2013) investigate the behavior of codeswitching and codemixing in English-Yoruba discourses. They find out that whereas codeswitching takes place at both intersentential and intrasentential levels, codemixing is always an intrasentential phenomenon. This finding makes the distinction between codemixing and intrasentential codeswitching redundant.

As can be seen from the various studies, Yoruba borrowings in English is under-investigated. It is this gap that the present study hopes to fill.

Theoretical framework

The linguistic theory adopted for this study is Prince and Smolensky (2004) Optimality Theory (OT) for the formalisation of phonological aspects of the data. Among other things, OT already has much work on loan adaptation than any other linguistic theories (Prince and Smolensky, 2004; McCarthy and Prince, 1993). In addition, OT is among the most popular linguistic theories of the 21st century, especially in phonology. Indeed, it is impossible to have a list of the top five developments in linguistic theories without mentioning OT (McCarthy, 2007). This theory allows for linguistic debates on loanwords and other forms of lexical borrowing among linguists, and these have resulted in universal agreements on many generalisations, some of which are relied upon in this study. OT is a descriptive phonological theory, founded on the principle of constraints ranking, violation, and interaction (Bolaji, 2016). OT considers language to be a system of conflicting constraints. The grammar of one language, the theory contends, incorporates claims about the grammars of all human languages. Thus, OT, unlike other phonological theories is inherently typological. In OT, attempts are usually made to discover how universal linguistic principles are parameterized by a language, and how each grammar is unique in its own right

(Oyebade, 2008; Bolaji, 2019). According to OT, constraints are universal; but cross-linguistic differences are accounted for by differences in *ranking*. Constraints in OT are violable. The candidate with minimum violation emerges the correct output form.

Methodology

Ten lexical items sourced from three dictionaries: *Oxford English Dictionary: The Definitive Record of The English Language (OED, 2020)*; *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary (OALD, 2020)* and *Daniel Jones English Pronouncing Dictionary (EPD, 2004)* (OED OALD & EPD) form the data for this study. The items were analysed according to their adaptation strategies and phonological processes they manifested. Following Prince (2016), the prosodic element (stress) was analysed as **X** (head of foot), **U** (nonhead of foot), **O** (syllable not parsed into foot), and **-** (edge of prosodic unit). In the final analysis, only trochee and iamb were attested. Then, the findings of this study are formalised within the theoretical framework of Optimality Theory (OT).

The data

The 10 lexical items analysed in this study are all listed. All 10 are written in their Standard Yoruba forms with tone marks and appropriate diacritics for ease of comparison with English adapted version. The same practice is followed in two of the dictionaries, except the EPD which does this sparingly. That is not surprising, considering that the EDP is a pronouncing dictionary. They are all nouns. This is not surprising; most loanwords in the world languages are nouns (Myers-Scotton and Jake, 2016). Two of the words are common nouns (*Agbádá, Gàrí*); three are personal names (*Şóyínka, Abiólá, Tòkunbò*); three are place names (*Ifè, Ìbàdàn, Òshogbo*); one is the name of a language (Yorùbá); one is the proper name of a tree (*Ìrókò*).

The analysis

The lexical borrowing in (1) to (10) listed and phonemically transcribed below are analysed in this section.

1. Ìbàdàn /ɪ' bæd. ə n/;

2. If è /'i:.fɛɪ/;
3. Yorùbá /'jɔrɔbə/;
4. Agbádá /æg'ba:də/ ;
5. Gàrí/'gæɪ/;
6. Şóyínka /sɔɪ'ɪŋ.kə/:
7. Abiólá /,æb.i'əʊ.lə/;
8. Ìrókò /ɪ'rəʊkəʊ/
9. Òshogbo /ə'ʃɔŋ.bəʊ/;
10. Tòkùnbò /tɔ'kɔmbəʊ/

The analysis comprises the phonemic transcription of each word, the phonological processes involved in their adaptation as well as secondary articulatory processes and their prosodic features with respect to stress assignment. The Yoruba language is, therefore, the Source Language (SL), the language supplying the borrowing items; English is the Recipient Language (RL), the language doing the borrowing.

Adaptation strategies

When words are borrowed from an SL into an RL, adaptation strategies are activated, not by the SL but by the RL. This is necessary since no two languages have exactly the same phonological inventory. Scholars (Adetugbo, 1993; Ajolore, 1982; Kenstowicz, 2006; Ladefoged & Johnson, 2015; Salami, 1982; Wells, 2016) have explained the phonological dissimilarities between Yoruba and English. The Yoruba language is syllable-timed; English is stressed-timed. The Yoruba language a tonal language; English is an intonational language. The voiced labiovelar stop [gb], and the voiceless labiovelar stop [kp], which employ two closures and two airstreams, are attested in Yoruba, but the English language lacks both labiovelars stops. Phonological differences such

as those indicated will call for a number of adaptation strategies whenever one of the two languages loans to the other.

1. Phonological processes

Phonological processes are linguistic strategies of a language to account for phonological changes that are induced by phonological environments (Abiodun, 2010). Five phonological processes for the adaptation of established loanwords can be identified. Among the common phonological processes identified in the literature are assimilation, elision, deletion, epenthesis, coalescence, metathesis, diphthongization, Monophthongization and harmony (Adetugbo, 1993; Awonusi, Ademola-Adeoye, & Adedeji, 2015; Oyebade, 2008). The identified phonological processes in the data for this study are discussed below.

Diphthongization

In this process, a unit of sound in Yoruba borrowing with a single place of articulation is adapted with two places of articulation. The targeted diphthongs are mainly closing diphthongs ending in /ɪ/ and /ʊ/. No case of centring diphthong is attested. The three closing diphthongs attested are /eɪ/, /əʊ/ and /ɔɪ/. The researchers observed that Yoruba loanwords with the oral vowels [è], [o], [ó], and [ó] are adapted as either /eɪ/, /əʊ/ or /ɔɪ/. As in (1) - (4)

1. [è] → /eɪ/ in *If è* /'i:.feɪ/
2. [ó] → /əʊ/ in *Ìrókò* /ɪ'rəʊkəʊ/, *Òshogbo* /ə'ʃɔg.bəʊ/
3. [ó] → /əʊ/ in *Abìólá* /,æb.i'əʊ.lə/
4. [ó] → /ɔɪ/ in *Ṣóyínká* /sɔɪ'ɪŋ.kə/

Three different cases of diphthongization [è] → /eɪ/ ; [o] and [ó] → /əʊ/ ; [ó] → /ɔɪ/ were identified. Of the three, /əʊ/ seems to be most productive; while /eɪ/ and /ɔɪ/ are less so. The English closing diphthong /əʊ/ is a vowel merger of two distinct phonemes [o] and [ó] in the SL. This is more like intelligibility failure on the part of the RL speakers, or perhaps, a case of sound perception or both. The Yoruba round vowel with the High Tone (HT) [ó] has two diphthongal realizations. It is either

realized as /əʊ/ in a disyllabic word, if there is a copy of the adapted phoneme post-consonantly in the SL for the sake of harmony or as /ɔɪ/, if there is no copy. Hence, there is a case of many-to-one phonemic adaptation.

Deletion

Only a single case of deletion was found, involving the palatal sound and semivowel /j/ or [y], in the word *Şóyínka* → /sɔɪ'ɪŋ.kə/, realizing the phonological description $x \rightarrow \emptyset$, in a process called *aphaeresis* (Awonusi, Ademola-Adeoye & Adedeji (2015). Deletion is a phonological process of removing, deleting or doing away with obstructive segments. Although it is often done with clusters, this example indicates that it can also take place elsewhere.

The case of deletion in this particular example is deserves some attention. First, after the palatal deletion, a front, high, oral vowel is added to a round back vowel realizing the closing diphthong /ɔɪ/ in anticipation of the next onsetless syllable beginning with /ɪ/. This may be a special kind of assimilation. If that is the case, then, the target of the assimilation is /ɪ/. Second is the deletion and replacement of the palatal sound /j/ with the high short vowel /ɪ/ in the penultimate stressed syllable [-ɪŋ-]. Such phonological processes are expected considering that this palatal sound also has the features of vowels; hence, it is called a semivowel. Ladefoged and Johnson (2015) observe that in the production of “*yell* or *yes*”, the movements of formants for /j/ are identical with the movement away from the short vowel /ɪ/ (p. 213).

Substitution

This occurs when there is no one-to-one correspondence between phonemic segments in the SL and the RL. Put differently, it is a phonetic-phonological process in which the particular phonetic form is not attested in the RL and has to be replaced by a closest phonemic neighbour in the RL's phonetic inventory. It affects both consonants and vowels.

1. [à] → /æ/ in *Gàrí'* gæri/
2. [a] → /æ/ in *Agbádá* /æg'ba:də/
3. [i] → /ɪ/ (word final) in *Gàrí'* gæri

4. [o] → /ɒ/ in Yorùbá /'jɔrɒbə/, Òshogbo /ə'ʃɔg.bəʊ/; /ə/ in Òshogbo /ə'ʃɔg.bəʊ/

In (1), [à] becomes /æ/ in-between two consonants, the voiced velar stop /g/ and the roll /r/, with the stress assigned to the first syllable where the substitution resides. In (2), [à] has multiple substitutions, depending on its phonological environments as shown in (1) to (4). It is substituted with /æ/ as a syllable without edges; /ɑ:/ in a stressed syllable, and /ə/ in unstressed syllables. The schwa replacement case is default for all unstressed syllables as can be seen in all ten examples.

Summary: [à] → /æ/, /ɑ:/, or /ə/. This is a case of vowel split in which a unit of sound has multiple realizations. The default seems to be /æ/; others are found elsewhere. So it is also a case of elsewhere condition. Thus, the vowel [à] in Yoruba can become any of the three vowels depending on the foot structure of the word. In all three realizations, /ə/ is unstressed.

In examples (3) and (4) the high, tense, front vowel [i] and the open, back tense vowel [o] in the SL, become the high, close lax vowel /ɪ/ and the open, back, lax vowel /ɒ/ in the RL respectively. It can be noted that close approximation and place of articulation are among the factors driving sound substitution.

Vowel reduction/Weakening

Vowel reduction in English occurs when a strong vowel is weakened to the schwa /ə/. Two vowels are usually used to achieve this, /ə/ and /ɪ/. The two forms are attested in this study, with the latter being more productive. Only two examples are discussed here.

Vowel weakening

1. [à] → /ə/ in Ìbàdàn /ɪ' bæd.ə n/

2. [i] → /ɪ/ in Gàrí/ 'gæri

Although this particular example falls under substitution, it is treated separately here because it involves weakening, a phonological process defined by Awonusi, Ademola-Adeoye and Adedeji (2015) as “a process of lenition” (p. 208). The process is often determined, as stated in this study by the absence or presence of stress.

Consonant Split

This is operative on the segments called labial velar, defined by Ladefoged and Johnson (2015) as sounds which “involve the simultaneous use of two gestures” (p. 182). Only the voiced labial velar /gb/ is attested. Perhaps, as a result of sonority plateau, in which the occurrence of peaks and valleys are blurred or absent (Wayland, 2019)

Examples:

1. Agbádá → /æg'ba:də/: gb→/b/, /d/
2. Òshogbo /ə'ʃɔŋ.bəʊ/: gb→/b/, /d/

Secondary Articulatory processes

Velarization

This is a secondary articulatory process in which a non-velar sound is realized as a velar nasal /ŋ/ ([n]→ŋ ; Šóyínká /sɔɪ'ŋ.kə/) because of its closeness to it. It involves tongue raising or raising of the velum, usually the back of the tongue, in a co-articulation for a sound without that feature. In the example of Šóyínká realised as /sɔɪ'ŋ.kə/, the native word has the alveolar nasal [n] preceded by a palatal sound [j]. In the adapted version, the alveolar nasal although requires a tongue raising to be articulated as a coronal sound, becomes a non-coronal velar sound having its raising elsewhere.

Labialization

In labialization, a non-labial sound is adapted as a labial sound. According to Abiodun (2010), “labialization occurs when a consonant that is produced without lip rounding becomes rounded due to the influence of a rounded vowel, mostly /u/” (p. 51).

[n] →/m/ as in Tòkumbò /tɔ'kumbəʊ/

Unlike what Abiodun predicted, labialization in this one and only example in this data occurs not just in an environment of a non-round vowel, but a nasalized vowel [u] with already lip-rounding feature in the SL. Thus, the labialization occurs, not in anticipation of a rounded vowel /u/, but in the environment of an obstruent /b/, with the phonological feature +labial, resulting in [n] →/m.

Vowel phonotactics

This is not a phonological process; it is a factor of phonological structure or sound distribution and occurrences. The data for vowel substitution can be charted by environment as specified in table 1.

Table 1: Vowel phonotactics

Vowel	Environment						
	#_____	_____#	_____	C____C	_____	C_____	V_____
[a] →/æ/	+	+		+		+	
[a] →/ə/	+	+		+			
[o] →/əʊ/	+	+					
[è] →eɪ		+					
[i] →/ɪ/	+					+	+

This table shows that in Yoruba borrowings in English (English-Yoruba borrowing), the locus of phonological operation is usually vowel [a]. Therefore, from all the examples of vowel behavior discussed in this study, vowel [a] has the highest phonotactic distribution.

Loan Prosody

Following Prince (2016), the prosodic elements (stress) in the loanword examples are analysed as **X** (head of foot), **U** (nonhead of foot), **O** (syllable not parsed into foot), and **-** (edge of prosodic unit). In the final analysis, only trochee and iamb were attested. With this analysis, the following feet are realized.

1. **-XU-** as in Gàrí/'gæri, If è /'i:.feɪ/, Yorùbá /'jɔrɒbə/

2. -UX- as in Agbádá /æg'ba:də/, Şóyínká /sɔi'ɪŋ.kə/, Abíólá /,æb.i'əu.lə/, Ìbàdàn /i'bæd. ə n/, Òshogbo /ə'ʃɔŋ.bəʊ/, Tòkumbò /tɔ'kumbəʊ/

According to the analysis, two prominent feet are attested in the loanword example, trochaic foot with head initial feature, and iambic foot, with head final feature. Out of the two feet, iambic foot is more prominent. This is in sharp contrast to the tone patterns of the words in the SL. The researcher concludes then contrary to what is observed by Kenstowicz (2006) in his analysis of tonal adaptation of English loanwords in Yoruba, where tone-stress mapping appears to be operative, there appears to be no tone-stress mapping in English-Yoruba loanwords. Table 1 provides a clear illustration of this argument.

Table 1. No Tone-Stress Mapping

WORD	SL SYLLABLE PATTERN	RL SYLLABLE PATTERN	TONAL PATTERN	STRESS PATTERN
Gàrí	CVCV	CVCV	LH	/X
Agbádá	VCVCV	VCCVCV	MHH	XX
Ìbàdàn	VCVCV	VCVCV	LLL	XX
Şóyínká	CVCVVCV	CVVC.CV	HHMH	XX
Abíólá	VCVVCV	VCVVCV	MHHH	XXX

Key: C =consonant, V=vowel, L/LT=Low Tone, H/HT= High Tone, M/MT= Mid Tone, X=unstressed, /=stress

According to table 1, whereas the Yoruba syllable pattern is adapted unchanged in RL, except in 'Şóyínká' and words with labiovelar in which case, a division always terminates with the voiced velar stop; and a new division starts with the voiced bilabial stop, no tone-stress mapping was found. However, there is variation in stress assignments. All tree-syllable loanwords receive their stress on the second syllable. This is true for *Agbádá*, *Ìbàdàn* and *Şóyínká*. Disyllabic words seem to receive their stress on the first syllable. Therefore, the disyllabic loan *gàrí* receives its stress on

the first syllable. As demonstrated by Bolaji (forthcoming), this appears to be the case for other dissyllabic words like *ẹbà*, *Ifẹ*, and *fùfù*. Heterosyllabic words receive their stress on the third syllable. Although further studies will have to confirm this generalization, the fact remains that there is no tone-stress mapping in Yoruba words in English.

Assimilation

Another adaptation phonological process in Yoruba loanwords in English is assimilation, a phonological process in which a phonological segment takes on the feature of a contiguous segment which is more sonorous than it (Ajiboye, 2020). Assimilation is among the most productive adaptation strategies in English whenever Yorùbá words are borrowed or loaned into its lexicon. At least, three cases are identified

n → **ŋ**

Şóyínka → Soyinka → /sɔɪ'ŋ.kə/

In the SL, the default consonant in both 'Şóyínka' and 'À̀nkara ' is [n]. This is realised as /ŋ/ in the RL, producing /sɔɪ'ŋ.kə/. This happens as a result of a progressive place assimilation which makes the alveolar nasal [n] becomes [ŋ], a velar nasal in anticipation of the velar stop /k/.

OT Account

In this section only two examples of OT formalism of the data are provided in two tableaux. The activated constraints are **LABIAVELAR (VOICE)**, a markedness constraint which forbids voiced labiovelar from surfacing; **PERCEPTION**, a faithfulness constraint which requires segments to be adapted as perceived, **MAX**, another faithfulness constraint which requires input to be maximally mapped into output, **DEP I-O** which requires input-output correspondence and **DEP_v** which disprefers vowel insertion. The set of constraints is ranked according to the requirements for the optimal candidate form in each table.

Ranking: LABIAVELAR (VOICE) >> PERCEPTION >> MAX

Tableau 1: Òşogbo /ə'ʃɔŋ.bəʊ/

Òşogbo /ə'ʃɔŋ.bəʊ/		LABIAVELAR (VOICE)	PERCEPTION	MAX I-O
a.	☞ /ə'ʃɔŋ.bəʊ/			
b.	/ə'ʃɔŋbəʊ/	*!	*!	*!
c.	[Òşogbo]	*!	*!	

The highest ranked constraint in tableau 4.40 is **LABIAVELAR (VOICE)** which forbids voiced labiovelar from occurring as adjacent consonants, forming a unit. This constraint is violated by other candidates except candidate (a) which produces the optimal candidate /ə'ʃɔŋ.bəʊ/. Although this surface form may sound odd to the ear of any SL speaker, the highest ranked constraint in the SL makes it the correct output form. In loan phonology, the RL, and not the SL, determines the best candidate.

Ranking: AGREEPLACE (nasal)>> DEP I-O>> DEP_v

Tableau 2: şóyínkà /sɔɪ'ɪŋ.kə/

şóyínkà /sɔɪ'ɪŋ.kə/		AGREEPLACE (nasal)	DEP I-O	DEP _v
a.	şóyínkà	*!		
b.	/sɔɪ'ɪ jɪ n.kə/	*!	*	*
c.	☞ /sɔɪ'ɪŋ.kə/			

Tableau 2 ranks constraints on a popular name, Şóyínkà adapted as /sɔɪ'ɪŋ.kə/. The highest ranked constraint in tableau 2 is **AGREEPLACE (nasal)** which requires the nasal sound to agree in the feature place with the adjacent segment. This constraint enforces place assimilation. Next in ranking to this constraint is **DEP I-O** which forbids insertion. Since this constraint requires the same thing as DEP_v even in a more encompassing way, there exist breaking lines between the two

constraints. Accordingly, only candidate ‘c’ satisfies all requirements for well-formedness. In the SL, the alveolar nasal [n] precedes the velar stop [k]. To be assimilated into English according to well-formedness condition, the alveolar nasal needs to be assimilated into the same place as the velar stop, in order to share the same feature values of anteriority and coronality [-ant] and [-cor]. The only candidate which satisfies **AGREEPLACE (nasal)** is candidate ‘c’ in which the alveolar nasal becomes a velar nasal /ŋ/ across syllable boundary, through the phonological process of velarization. Other candidates lost out.

Conclusion

Yoruba loanwords in English have peculiar features. They are basically nominal expressions, which may manifest as proper nouns, common nouns and agree in person and number with their verbs, even though they were never used in any sentence in this paper. They are adopted into English through such phonological processes as assimilation, diphthongization, substitution, and secondary articulatory processes like velarization and labialization, among others. It was also discovered that there were no cases of tone-stress mapping as argued in similar researches on other languages such as Yoruba. The constraint most ranked in the data analysed was **AGREEPLACE (nasal)**, which subjects to the operation of assimilation. It is a fact that Yoruba borrowings in English have come of age. Since this is a pilot study, more study will be needed to fully discuss how Yoruba borrowing are adapted into English, in order to discover their contributions to contact linguistics.

Recommendations

This study makes two recommendations. First, more studies on English-Yoruba borrowings should be conducted. Second, more research should be carried out in African contact linguistics.

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